

Research-in-Progress Paper

Beyond policy experimentation to political praxis: Citizenship formation through Living Labs

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Abstract

This study reconceptualises Living Labs as democratic spaces for the political formation of citizens, beyond their conventional role as tools for technological experimentation or policy implementation. Drawing on the theoretical framework of deliberation, subjectivation, and praxis, it explores how citizens transition from passive policy recipients to active political subjects through participation in Living Labs. Rather than focusing on institutional outcomes, the study examines how citizens engage in ethical and practical reflection to define public problems, co-create solutions, and enact change within their lived contexts. Methodologically, the study adopts an interpretive, concept-led approach, analysing two Living Lab cases conducted in 2024: a climate disaster alert project and a citizen-led carbon neutrality initiative. These cases illustrate how deliberative and co-creative processes can foster reflexivity, judgement, and transformation. However, the paper also cautions against idealising participation, highlighting the need to address issues of power, exclusion, and diversity for Living Labs to fulfil their democratic potential. Ultimately, Living Labs are positioned as experimental infrastructures for lived democracy, where publicness is reconstructed through practice and where marginalised voices can articulate new claims to citizenship. This approach aligns with Deweyan pragmatism and affirms democracy as an ongoing process of becoming, not a static institutional form.

Key words

Living Lab, Political Subjectivation, Deliberative Democracy, Citizenship Formation, Co-creation, praxis

Introduction

Modern democracy has long operated within a procedural framework centered on voting and representation. Yet within such confines, citizens often remain objects of politics, with limited opportunities to recognize or take responsibility for public issues in their daily lives. This institutional fixation risks mechanisms of exclusion, erasing the everyday and sensorial foundations of politics. Living Labs transcend these limitations by creating spaces where citizens can define public problems, participate in their resolution, and experiment with political imagination. Here, democracy becomes a “way of life”—a skill cultivated through sensorial experience and practice—enabling citizens to move from policy recipients to political subjects engaged in deliberation and action.

Rather than viewing Living Labs merely as instruments for technological experimentation or policy acceptance, this study repositions them as processes of citizen subject formation. The guiding question is therefore: How do Living Labs contribute to the formation of citizens’ political subjectivity and democratic practice? Unlike Fishkin’s Deliberative Polling, which focuses on shifts in public opinion, Living Labs constitute a broader democratic experiment involving practical intervention and transformation of subjectivity. This perspective resonates with American pragmatism, particularly John Dewey’s conception of democracy as a process of collective recognition and problem-oriented practice rather than a fixed institution. Living Labs embody this orientation by reconstructing publicness through practice and experimenting with democracy at the level of everyday life. To ground this argument, the paper also engages with established Living Lab scholarship, including Schuurman (2015, 2016), Leminen and Westerlund (2012, 2017), Nyström et al. (2014), and Steen and van Bueren (2017), situating the study within the wider field of innovation, governance, and collaborative experimentation.

Theoretical Framework

This study analyses the political potential of Living Labs by focusing on three interrelated concepts: deliberation, subjectivation, and praxis. Here, praxis refers not merely to repetitive actions but to transformative practices grounded in political judgment and ethical responsibility, aimed at resolving community issues.

Figure 1. A Framework for Citizenship Formation in Living Labs

Deliberation materializes in co-creation, where citizens and stakeholders jointly define problems, construct solutions, and explore practices within their everyday contexts. This process extends beyond information exchange to include value conflicts, coordination, emotional sharing, and judgment. Citizens repeatedly ask themselves: “Why am I involved in this issue?”, “How is this connected to my life?”, and “What kind of society do I want to help create?” Through this questioning, they constitute themselves as public actors. Subjectivation unfolds within this chain of deliberation and response, with Living Labs serving as arenas for such subject formation. The cyclical interaction of deliberation, subjectivation, and praxis is illustrated in Figure 1, which captures the recursive process through which citizens transform both themselves and their communities.

While this conceptual triad explains the internal dynamics of subject formation, Living Labs are also embedded in broader institutional arrangements. The Helix approaches provide a useful lens here. Beginning with Etzkowitz and Leydesdorff’s (2000) Triple Helix of university–industry–government relations, the framework has expanded into the Quadruple Helix, adding civil society and culture (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009), and the Quintuple Helix, incorporating environmental sustainability (Carayannis & Rakhmatullin, 2014). These extensions have broadened the focus from technological innovation to social innovation, civic participation, and sustainability. Yet, conventional Helix models often appear static, overlooking the temporal dynamics, shifting power relations, and heterogeneous subjectivities that shape participatory processes. As Leminen (2015) shows, stakeholders in Living Labs shift functions across project phases, while Nyström et al. (2014) highlight the multidimensional and evolving nature of actors’ contributions.

Building on these insights, this study reinterprets the Helix not as a fixed structure but as a dynamic constellation in which actors assume complementary roles. Citizens articulate problems from lived experience; artists stimulate imagination through sensory expression; researchers analyse and structure ideas; policymakers translate proposals into institutional measures; companies provide resources and technologies; and journalists and media amplify narratives to wider audiences. Figure 2 visualizes this reinterpretation, depicting actor roles as fluid yet interdependent, and positioning Living Labs as sustainable arenas of democratic experimentation rather than static institutional schemes.

Figure 2. Reinterpreted Helix Model of Stakeholder Collaboration

Taken together, Figures 1 and 2 provide a comprehensive framework for analysing the democratic potential of Living Labs. Figure 1 depicts the internal cycle of deliberation, subjectivation, and praxis through which citizenship is constituted, while Figure 2 highlights their external embedding within dynamic multi-stakeholder constellations, where diverse actors assume complementary roles in co-creation. Combined, these perspectives present Living Labs as both transformative spaces of citizen formation and structurally embedded arenas of participatory governance.

Methodology

The study adopts an interpretive, concept-led approach. It explores how citizens narrate, reflect upon, and enact their participation. Data are analysed through qualitative coding, focusing on how language, experiences, and actions reveal the interplay of deliberation, subjectivation, and praxis. Two Living Lab cases conducted in South Korea in 2024 provide empirical grounding. These cases were selected not for representativeness but

for their capacity to illustrate the political processes of deliberation, subjectivation, and praxis within concrete participatory settings.

Climate Disaster Alert Living Lab (February 2024)

Organized as part of the Ministry of Environment’s Climate Adaptation R&D Program, this Lab involved seven citizens aged 20s–60s, including elderly individuals and parents, alongside three experts in technology, communication, and journalism. Participants co-created prototypes of disaster alert messages aimed at enhancing clarity and trust. Data sources included audio recordings, field notes, message drafts, and analytical coding.

Figure 3. Living Lab Process

Citizen-Led Carbon Neutrality Living Lab (July–August 2024)

Jointly organized by the University of Seoul and Dongdaemun District, this Lab engaged 15 undergraduate students in six weekly sessions aimed at translating carbon neutrality into actionable practices for everyday life. To complement group discussions, ten follow-up interviews were conducted in September 2024, each lasting about one hour. Qualitative analysis of the transcripts traced how abstract concepts were reinterpreted through lived experience and translated into participatory, co-creative practices.

Empirical Analysis

In both Living Lab cases, deliberation was the entry point. Participants began by critically reflecting on the inadequacies of existing systems. In the disaster alert case, citizens

pointed out that messages lacked concrete behavioural guidance and that repeated, identical alerts from multiple authorities created confusion and fatigue. These discussions moved beyond complaints, raising fundamental questions about the purpose of alerts: Were they intended to raise awareness, provide actionable guidance, or shift responsibility onto citizens? This revealed tensions between efficiency and relevance, expert authority and everyday usability. Deliberation here extended beyond information exchange to include value conflicts, negotiation of responsibility, and articulation of lived experiences. In the carbon neutrality lab, students and community members debated whether small-scale actions—such as turning off lights or using tumblers—could meaningfully address the climate crisis. Some welcomed behavioural change, while others remained sceptical. These discussions created a contested space where doubts and hopes coexisted.

Yet deliberation alone was not sufficient. Participants were invited to co-create concrete solutions. Through group exercises, scenario design, and prototype testing, citizens moved from abstract debate to tangible outputs. In the disaster alert lab, participants collaboratively redesigned messages with clearer sender identification, expert-backed guidance, and links for further information. This process was central to subjectivation. By seeing their proposals taken seriously by experts, citizens experienced a shift in self-perception: their contributions were no longer “just ideas” but could be considered for real application. In the carbon neutrality lab, co-creation took the form of action plans for students and local communities. While the immediate impact seemed modest, participants reported a stronger sense of responsibility and efficacy. One student reflected: “Through the Living Lab, I realized I was not only consuming knowledge but also participating as a producer of it.” This highlights how co-creation and subjectivation are tightly linked, reconstituting participants as agents of political agency. The culmination of these processes was praxis: the enactment of actions with both practical and democratic significance. In the disaster alert case, participants continued testing and refining message prototypes. In the carbon neutrality lab, students committed to small but concrete actions. Praxis was not merely about implementation; it also involved reflexivity and tension. Some participants doubted whether small contributions could matter, while others argued that incremental change could build momentum for structural transformation. This ambivalence reflects Dewey’s view of democratic experimentation as inherently provisional outcomes are not final solutions but steps in an ongoing process of inquiry and adjustment. One interviewee summarized: “Living Labs complemented representative democracy as an active form of democracy, but it was disappointing that we could not monitor whether our ideas were actually incorporated into policy.”

Importantly, praxis linked individual transformation to institutional structures. While behavioural changes signalled agency, their democratic significance emerged only when coupled with institutional uptake—for example, through municipal adaptation plans or university policies. This demonstrates that the political potential of Living Labs lies in creating feedback loops between citizen subjectivation, collective co-creation, and institutional governance. As Biesta (2011) argues, citizenship is an ongoing ethical process of becoming, and as Isin and Nielsen (2008) emphasize, it is enacted through practice rather than bestowed solely as institutional rights. The praxis observed here thus demonstrates how lived democratic experimentation reconstitutes citizens as active political subjects.

Discussion

This analysis shows that Living Labs are not simply participatory tools but experimental arenas where citizens become political subjects through deliberation, co-creation, and praxis. The findings contribute in three ways. First, Living Labs bridge deliberative and experimental democracy, moving from communicative deliberation (Habermas) to experiential experimentation (Dewey) and embodying a hybrid form of discursive and practical democracy. Second, they highlight the centrality of co-creation in subjectivation: citizens' self-perception shifted when their proposals were incorporated into expert discussions, transforming them from policy recipients to agents. Third, they underscore the conditional nature of praxis: behavioural changes and initiatives gained democratic significance only when supported by institutional uptake. As one participant reflected, “Living Labs may not change the whole system at once, but they change how we see ourselves in relation to the system.” Yet the realization of this potential depends on certain prerequisites. Participation must extend beyond user feedback to foster processes of self-formation and political engagement. Effective deliberation requires diversity, recognition of power asymmetries, and sensitivity to cultural and emotional differences. Without these, Living Labs risk devolving into depoliticized exercises in technology acceptance.

Despite these risks, Living Labs possess distinctive democratic potential. Following Rancière (1999), they create moments where marginalized groups articulate issues in their own terms, echoing Rawls's principle of prioritizing the least advantaged. Deliberation, understood with Dryzek (2000) as including emotion, culture, and identity, thus becomes an ethical practice of recognizing conflict and fostering public justification (Gutmann & Thompson, 2004). Living Labs can therefore be conceived as ethical-political spaces where citizens constitute themselves as public actors. Their distinctiveness lies not in

technological novelty but in reactivating democracy as lived practice. Innovation here means reconfiguring relationships and participation rather than producing artefacts. From a Foucauldian perspective, Living Labs are also political technologies—sites where power, subjectivation, and imagination intersect. Conceived in this way, they foreground the politics of design and governance and open new directions for democratic theory and practice.

Conclusion

Living Labs, as demonstrated in these cases, operate as experimental sites where citizens become political subjects through the interrelated processes of deliberation, co-creation, and praxis. They not only generate innovative responses to climate-related challenges but also cultivate experiential forms of democracy that connect individual transformation with institutional governance. Rather than treating Living Labs as mere tools for technological experimentation, this study reconfigures them as spaces of political formation and democratic practice. Citizens, through cycles of reflection and collective action, emerge as co-constructors of publicness instead of passive recipients. By drawing on and reinterpreting frameworks such as the 4/5 Helix alongside established Living Lab scholarship, the study underscores how democracy can be reconstructed as an everyday practice. In an era of deepening distrust in institutions, the significance of Living Labs lies in transforming participation into political subjectivation and embedding publicness within daily contexts. Future research should build on this theoretical foundation by empirically examining the micro-politics of power, subjectivity, and participation, thereby advancing our understanding of Living Labs as political technologies.

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